

NFDI4Earth

Milestone MS1.2.1

Criteria and requirements for Incubator project

NFDI4Earth Incubators

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Executive summary

This document outlines the expectations, the criteria, as well as the call and the review of incubator projects.

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1. Criteria and call

A set of criteria and requirements have been defined, in order to clarify, which types of proposals are qualified for an incubator project. This is mainly

- New research, also blue-sky ideas, related to all aspects of the NFDI4Earth, including – but not limited to:
 - automatic metadata extraction and annotation
 - machine learning, data interpretation, and data fusion
 - visualization, and interaction
 - ...
- Focusing on tools and methods

2. Expected deliverable

The expected outputs was shortly described in the call:

- reproducible software
- easy to install and understand. e.g., containing proper documentation and example data (e.g., in terms of GitLab)
- easy to apply, containing small tutorials or examples, e.g., Jupyter-notebook

The final deliverable were collected at the GitLab from the RWTH Aachen. Therefore, a template project was created for each project, which includes:

- Project description a pdf file including an abstract (a half page), which focusing the question: "What is new?".
- tutorial.ipynb a Jupyter notebook, which is ideally ready for access via Binder.
- CITATION.cff a meta data file.
- LICENSE a file with the license details.
- README.md with the sections:
 - How to install
 - How to use
 - How to cite

- References
- Acknowledgment with the funding information: "This work has been funded by the German Research Foundation (NFDI4Earth, DFG project no. 460036893, <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>)".

3. Evaluation criteria

The evaluation of the proposal will be guided along three categories – each category will be scored from 1 (poor) to 5 (excellent) and a total grade will be derived using the weighting indicated below.

1. Quality and Innovation (weight 40%)

- is the idea convincing?
- Does it solve an interesting / relevant problem?
- is it new (in the field)?
- Is the ambition adequate?

2. Feasibility (weight 40%)

- Does the researcher have the required expertise?
- Is the research plan feasible?
- Does it use or extend existing technologies? Or is it a novel innovation?

3. Potential for transferability (weight 20%)

- Ability to process similar data from different time periods / locations / institutions

Also, the goal is to be maximally inclusive and thus also targets at new partners to the NFDI4Earth. Therefore, given equal quality of proposals, in selection process will prefer proposals from new partners and shorter projects.

All these requirements have been described in a document, which was delivered in the call (see document on following page). The document also includes the evaluation criteria, so that it is clear for the applicants, on which elements to concentrate. Also it describes the funding volume.

In addition, a template for the proposal was given, which the applicants should adhere to (see document on following pages).

4. Review

The review was originally designed to be an open review process, meaning that both the proposals and the anonymous reviews will be made accessible. However, after careful consideration, the Co-Applicant-team decided to refrain from it and stick to a single blind procedure. The rationale was that it firstly might discourage applicants to see their proposal and the (negative) reviews listed publicly; also, it was seen that there is a potential risk of stealing ideas.

Each proposal was reviewed by 5 evaluators. This led to a ranking of all proposals. In a decision in a meeting with all co-apps, the evaluations were looked at and checked for consistency, outliers, etc. In case of equal quality, other aspects were taken into account, namely, discipline, topic domain, institutional balance, new partners, regional distribution.

A. Call for incubator projects

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Preamble - Incubator Projects for the NFDI4Earth

1st call - Submission Deadline: May 13, 2022

The objective of the Incubator Lab is to foster the exploration of new, potentially relevant building blocks to be included in the NFDI4Earth and related NFDIs. The Incubator Lab invites proposals on novel cutting-edge tools, latest innovations, and high-risk blue-sky ideas. Incubator Projects are supposed to be small, concise, and have a clear focus. The funding duration of each project is therefore limited to 3-6 months for one researcher (DFG personnel rate). In total, in this call up to 8 projects can be funded.

Eventually, all the funded projects will contribute to a repository of advanced tools to improve the use and usability of NFDI4Earth data, advancing the state-of-the-art and to better meet (current and future) user needs.

How to apply for an NFDI4Earth Incubator Project?

Submissions should focus on tools and methods, and can relate to all aspects of the NFDI4Earth, including, but not limited to:

- automatic metadata extraction and annotations,
- machine learning, data interpretation, data fusion,
- visualization and interaction,
- ...

Expected outputs should be, for example

- reproducibility software,
- easy to install and well documented with example data (preferably in GitLab),
- easy to apply, including small tutorials or examples, e.g., as a Jupyter-notebook,
- ...

Application and evaluation process:

Any researcher can apply, who is affiliated or hosted by a German research institution. In the latter case, a letter of confirmation from the host is required along with the proposal submission. (If you do not have a host, please feel free to contact the NFDI4Earth Coordination Office.)

Incubator Projects must be described concisely; the proposal must not exceed 3 pages. Submissions should follow the template ([Template Incubator](#)). Proposals for Incubator Projects will be evaluated in an open review process. Both the proposals and the anonymous reviews will be made accessible. By submitting a proposal, you as PI agree to an open-access evaluation of the proposal.

The proposal will be assessed in three categories – each category will be scored from 1 (poor) to 5 (excellent) and a total grade will be derived using the weighting indicated below:

- Quality and Innovation (weight 40%)
 - Is the idea convincing?

- Does it solve an interesting / relevant problem?
- Is it new (in the field)?
- Is the ambition adequate?
- Feasibility (weight 40%)
 - Does the researcher have the required expertise?
 - Is the research plan feasible?
 - Does it use or extend existing technologies? Or is it a novel innovation?
- Potential for transferability (weight 20%)
 - Ability to process similar data from different time periods / locations / institutions

We want to be maximally inclusive and invite new partners to the NFDI4Earth. Therefore, given equal quality of proposals, in selection process

- proposals from new partners are preferred,
- shorter projects are preferred.

Please submit your proposal via:

<https://www.geo-x.net/nfdi4earth-incubators/application-form/>

Note: If the submitted incubator project proposal is successful, the applicant and host (if applicable) agree that

- the PI's parent institution will be named as Participant (with the PI as representative) of the NFDI4Earth,
- a letter of commitment (LoC) will be provided if the institution of the PI is not yet a Participant in NFDI4Earth (due to DFG regulations the letter has to be signed by your institution),
- the so called 'funds transfer and cooperation agreement' must be signed as Participant (Institution) for funding.

Also note: The submission is subject to a review process and does not guarantee any funding!

FAQ Incubator Projects

What should be included in the LoC?

- Running an NFDI4Earth Incubator Project requires you to become a Participant in NFDI4Earth. If your institution is not yet a Participant in NFDI4Earth, we would ask you to send a Letter of Commitment. The template for the partner's LoC is available on request.

For what kind of resources can we apply?

- You may only apply for staff costs, 3 to 6 months full-time equivalent (FTE).

I have a great idea, but I am not affiliated to a research organization. Can I still participate?

- Yes, good ideas are welcome! Please find a host either from the list of participants, or from a German research organization. Your host has to confirm the willingness. If you do not find a host, please contact us.

From whom can I request further information or answers to further questions?

NFDI4Earth

- Feel free to send an email to nfdi4earth-info@groups.tu-dresden.de (Coordination Office) or yu.feng@ikg.uni-hannover.de

B. Pilot template

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PROJECT TITLE - NOT LONGER THAN ONE LINE

Name Lastname¹, Name Lastname², Name Lastname¹, and Name Lastname²

¹Affiliation

²Affiliation

Date of submission

Abstract

We expect a summary of the pilot organized as follows (one sentence for each point): 1. General introduction to scientific context/or overarching science question, 2. Concrete problem under scrutiny, 3. Objective of the pilot (max. two sentences), 4. Expected results, 5. Stakeholders of the pilot 6. Perspective of the pilot - if successful - for advancing the NFDI4Earth as a whole (max. two sentences).

I. Introduction

Needs to explain the following questions

- What is the scientific context? Or what is the overarching science question?
- What is the data-challenge you face and what is the state-of-the-art?
- What is the vision if your challenge would be solved?

II. Pilot description

Describes the Pilot (can also include a flow-chart).

- What is the technological backbone you rely upon?
- Which are the standards and interoperability approaches used in the pilot's context?
- What is the proposed solution?
- What is the innovation compared to the status quo?

III. Relevance for the NFDI4Earth

Explains integration and uptake potential.

- What are expected users and stakeholders and how do they benefit (describe your stakeholders referencing the following general archetypes: scientists, data curator, infrastructure provider, system integrator, university teacher, public authority, decision-maker)?
- What is the potential for other sub-branches in the Earth System Sciences?
- What elements of FAIR are particularly addressed?
- What aspects of the research data life cycle are particularly addressed?
- Are there particular contributions that help the NFDI4Earth to engage with (e.g. innovative methods, education, advancing interoperability, new platforms,...)?

IV. Deliverables

List the names and specifications of the two deliverables:

- Technical operability of the pilot (e.g. software shared, developed interface, implementation and dissemination of knowledge/data etc.).
- Roadmap document for the community (we expect a title of the roadmap you plan to deliver).

V. Work Plan & Requested funding

- Provide a milestone plan (or Gantt Chart) for the planned (up to) one-year implementation phase
- The maximum threshold for a funding request is a one year full time equivalent